

Thiopegan Derivatives. Part XXIX. Orientation Studies in 10,11-Thiopegans

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10,11-Thiopegans on nitration and bromination furnish 6-nitro and 6-bromo derivatives respectively. The position of the nitro group has been confirmed by oxidation of one of the nitrothiopegans with chromic acid and that of the bromo group by direct synthesis.

The nitration of 10,11-thiopegans¹ (I) was accomplished by heating them in a mixture of boiling acetic acid and nitric acid for 2-3 minutes, the products obtained being mononitro derivatives. Prolonged heating ruptured the thiopegan ring system. Nitration with other nitrating mixtures, like sulphuric acid and nitric acid or sulphuric acid and fuming nitric acid, did not yield satisfactory results.

The nitro group could preferably enter the position 2 or 6 in the thiopegan molecule. To ascertain the orientation, 2-chloro-5-nitrothiazoles² (IV: R=Cl, Br) were condensed with anthranilic acid. The products (V: R=Cl, Br), thus obtained, were found to be different from the products obtained by nitration. Since 5-nitroanthranilic acid could not be condensed with the chlorothiazoles³, confirmation of the structures by direct comparison with 6-nitrothiopegans was not possible. The oxidative degradation of the nitrothiopegans, obtained by nitration of (I: R=H), furnished 6-nitrobenzoyleurea⁴ (III), as is evident from its melting point and other properties. This confirms the orientation in the thiopegan molecule, the position 6 being the most active.

The condensation of 2-chlorothiazoles with various anthranilic acids³ generally provides low yields of thiopegans, whereas better yields (38%) are obtained with 2-chloro-5-nitrothiazoles. It has a good bearing on the mechanism of the condensation of 2-chlorothiazoles with amines or amino-acids.

The reaction is initiated by electrophilic nature of C-2, but the same is seriously reduced by the presence of unshared pairs of electrons on sulphur, as shown in compound (VI). Presence of nitro group in 5-position not only increases the positive charge on C-2 by the electromeric shifts but can also derive electrons from sulphur, as shown in structure (IV) leading to enhanced reactivity.

Bromination of 10, 11-thiopegans (X) was effected at the room temperature in chloroform medium in presence of pyridine, using two molecular equivalents of bromine. In absence of pyridine, the liberated hydrobromic acid formed hydrobromide with the un-

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1. Narang and Sachdev, *this Journal*, 1955, 32, 631.
2. *Science & Culture*, 1964, in press.
3. Narang *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1955, 32, 427.
4. Naraton *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 41, 2052.

changed thiopegan, which was precipitated, thus escaping bromination. Bromination with less than two-molecular proportion of bromine furnished a mixture of brominated and unchanged thiopegans.

(I)

(R=H, Me, Cl, Br)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

(V)

(VI)

(VII)

(VIII)

(IX)

(X)

The analytical data of the brominated products corresponded with monobromothiopegans, which were confirmed to be 6-bromo-10,11-thiopegans (IX) (Table I) by undepressed mixed m.p. with the authentic samples prepared by condensing 5-bromo-

anthranilic acid (VII) with 2-chlorothiazoles (VIII) by the method of Narang *et al.*¹ (Table II). The thiopegans resisted polybromination even under forcing conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Nitration of 3-Phenyl-2,9-diene-4-keto-10,11-thiopegan (I: R=H).—3-Phenyl-2,9-diene-4-keto-10,11-thiopegan (1.4 g.) was added to a mixture of glacial acetic acid (2 ml) and HNO₃ (4 ml, *d* 1.42) and the mixture heated on a water bath. The solid dissolved and after 2-3 min. brown fumes of oxides of nitrogen evolved. The reaction mixture was immediately poured in water (15 ml) and the product collected by suction, treated with sodium carbonate solution, filtered, and crystallised from acetic acid in golden yellow shining needles, m.p. 291°, yield 16%. (Found: C, 59.74; H, 3.17. C₁₆H₉O₃N₃S requires C, 59.44; H, 2.8%).

Nitration of 3-(p-Methyl)-phenyl-2,9-diene-4-keto-10,11-thiopegan (I: R = Me).—3-(*p*-Methyl)phenyl-2,9-diene-4-keto-10,11-thiopegan (1.4 g.) was dissolved in minimum amount of boiling glacial acetic acid. It was removed from the flame and to it was quickly added HNO₃ (4 ml, *d* 1.42) with stirring. It was then heated on a low flame for 2-3 min. till the colour of the solution became yellow. It was at once poured on water (50 ml) and the solid collected by suction. It was treated with sodium carbonate solution, filtered, washed free of sodium carbonate, and crystallised from acetic acid in golden yellow needles, m.p. 328°, yield 8%. (Found: C, 60.56; H, 3.09; N, 12.36. C₁₇H₁₁O₃N₃S requires C, 60.53; H, 3.26; N, 12.46%).

Nitration of 3-(p-Chloro)phenyl-2,9-diene-4-keto-10,11-thiopegan (I: R=Cl) was effected in the same way as above (I: R=Me) and crystallised in golden yellow needles from acetic acid, m.p. 340°, yield 8%. (Found: N, 11.70. C₁₆H₈O₃N₃ClS requires N, 11.72%).

Nitration of 3-(p-Bromo)phenyl-2,9-diene-4-keto-10,11-thiopegan (I: R=Br) was effected in the same way as (I: R=Me) and crystallised in golden yellow needles from acetic acid, m.p. 357°, yield 8.5%. (Found: C, 47.86; H, 1.96; N, 10.56. C₁₆H₈O₃N₃BrS requires C, 47.76; H, 1.99; N, 10.45%).

Oxidation of the Nitro Product obtained by Nitration of 3-Phenyl-2,9-diene-4-keto-10,11-thiopegan.—To a hot solution of the nitro product (0.8 g.) in acetic acid (50 ml) was added a solution of chromic acid (1 g.) in water (10 ml). A brisk reaction occurred. Acetic acid was removed; the residue was treated with water and filtered. The solid was basified with sodium carbonate solution; the insoluble solid was collected and crystallised from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 330° (decomp.). It is soluble in aqueous NaOH and contains nitrogen but no sulphur. Its melting point corresponds with that of 6-nitrobenzoyleneurea. The basic filtrate on acidification with HCl (dil.) furnished a compound, which after crystallisation from dilute ethanol melted at 121°. It was confirmed to be benzoic acid in the usual way.

2-Nitro-3-(p-chloro)phenyl-2,9-diene-4-keto-10,11-thiopegan (V: R = Cl).—Anthranilic acid (1.4 g.), 2-chloro-4-(*p*-chloro)phenyl-5-nitrothiazole (2.8 g.), HCl (conc., 2 drops), and phenol (5 ml) were heated to 140° for 8-10 min. till a yellow compound separated. It was allowed to cool to the room temperature and basified with sodium carbonate solution. The solid was collected by suction and crystallised from acetic acid in golden yellow needles, m.p. 243°, yield 38%. (Found: N, 11.4. C₁₆H₈O₃N₃ClS requires N, 11.7%).

2-Nitro-3-(*p*-bromo)phenyl-2,9-diene-4-keto-10,11-thiopegan (V : R = Br).—Anthranilic acid and 2-chloro-4-(*p*-bromo)phenyl-5-nitrothiazole were condensed in the same way as above. It was crystallised in golden yellow needles from acetic acid, m.p. 230°, yield 37%. (Found: N, 10.6. $C_{16}H_9O_3N_3BrS$ requires N, 10.45%).

Bromination of 2,9-Diene-4-keto-10,11-thiopegans.—To a solution of 10,11-thiopegan (0.01M) and pyridine (0.01M) in chloroform (30 ml) was added a solution of bromine (0.02M) in chloroform (10 ml) during 10 min. with stirring. Chloroform was distilled and the residue treated with water to dissolve pyridine hydrobromide. The insoluble solid was collected by suction and crystallised from acetic acid as silvery white flakes (Table I).

TABLE I
Bromination of thiopegans.

2,9-Dieno-10,11-thiopega-4-ones.	Product formed (IX).		% Yield.	M.P.	Found.	Reqd.
	R ₁ .	R ₂ .				
3-Phenyl-	Ph	H	78	203-204°	N : 7.70% S : 8.76 Br : 22.60	7.84% 8.96 22.41
3-(<i>p</i> -Chloro) phenyl-	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	H	74	246°	C : 49.22 H : 2.22 N : 7.09	49.04 2.04 7.15
3-(<i>p</i> -Bromo) phenyl-	<i>p</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄	H	73	270°	C : 44.41 H : 2.18 N : 6.05	44.04 1.84 6.42
2,3-Dimethyl-	Me	Me	70	209°	N : 8.90 S : 9.90	9.06 10.36

6-Bromo-2,9-diene-4-keto-10,11-thiopegans.—To a mixture of 5-bromoanthranilic acid (0.01 M), 2-chlorothiazole (0.01M), and phenol (5 ml) was added HCl (conc., 2 drops) and the mixture was heated in an oil bath at 150-60° for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was basified with sodium carbonate solution and filtered. The solid mass was boiled with ethanol (15 ml) and filtered hot by suction to remove the ethanol-soluble intractable sticky mass. Crystallisation from acetic acid furnished silvery white compounds, found identical with the products obtained in the previous experiments, by mixed m.p. (Table II).

TABLE II

2-Chlorothiazoles.	Product formed (IX).		% Yield.	*Mixed m.p.
	R ₁ .	R ₂ .		
4-(phenyl	Ph	H	18	203-204°
4-(<i>p</i> -chloro)phenyl-	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	H	20	246°
4-(<i>p</i> -bromo)phenyl-	<i>p</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄	H	12	270°
4-(<i>p</i> -methyl)phenyl-	Me	Me	39	209°

*Mixed m.p. with corresponding brominated thiopegan (Table I)